

Simplifying access to healthcare data with a Pediatric Health Data Space (PHDS)

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Healthcare research is challenging due to fragmented data and varying national regulations. To address this issue in the children's healthcare domain, the Pediatric Health Data Space connects hospitals in a mutual trust network.

In the PHEMS project, we're developing a PHDS - a groundbreaking solution addressing the challenges of secondary use of patient data for benchmarking and research.

Tietoevry's latest blog delved into the concept behind PHDS, built on federated data processing and decentralized trust. Check it out [here](#).

Watch Antti Kettunen from Tietoevry on webinar about the Design of the PHDS (40 min) [here](#).

